

Influence of motivation on teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West local government, Kwara State

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ABSTRACT

Motivation is the vital tool that can enhance effectiveness and aid good performance. Individual job performance and behaviour depend greatly on motivational factors. A number of studies have been done in the area of motivation for teachers and its benefits towards better performance for the students. The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of motivation on teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. Adopted research design for this study was the descriptive survey method. The respondents comprises of 150 teachers which were simple randomly selected from 10 schools in Ilorin West. The instrument that was used for collecting data for this study was adopted from Ayuba (2017) titled Motivation and Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire (MTEQ). Frequency count, percentage and mean score were used to answer research questions while Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) and t-test were employed to test the research hypothesis. Findings revealed that teachers' effectiveness is low and there was no significant influence of motivation on teachers' effectiveness.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education being a vehicle for development has placed teachers in a delicate, sensitive position in nation building. Unfortunately, Nigerian teachers are lowly regarded and poorly remunerated. This makes teaching an occupation that is taken as a last resort when there is no other alternative [1]. Individual job performance and behaviour depend greatly on motivational factors like salary, condition of service, promotion and the likes. These motivational factors are also important to teachers as a means of enhancing their effectiveness and performance on the job [2].

Motivation is concerned with the extent to which an individual does something or abstains from doing things. Job satisfaction is the main change of motivation in the educational system and perhaps may be seen in the same perspective with instructional knowledge, educational resources and techniques in the proliferation of learning goals and objectives. According to Aslam *et al* [3] motivation influences higher teachers' effectiveness and constitutes a remedy to meet most of the administrative problems in Nigerian educational institutions. Motivation according to Eyare [4] is essentially made-up an individual's basic needs and the conscious efforts made by the employer to gratify those needs. Since the success or otherwise of educational system rests on the quality and caliber of instructors, no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Motivating teachers to put in their best and be satisfied should be given priority by the government.

Aslam *et al* [3] emphasize that adequate remuneration, promotion as at when due, regular payment of salaries, study leaves, compensation and the likes are good motivators for good performance of any teacher. Similarly, Ondigho, worker most especially in the private organization highly motivated when there is regular incentives such prompt payment of salary, positive reward and when they are part of the decision making process [5].

As stated by Scorza [6], education is a fundamental human right and the basic focus to peace, stability and sustainable development of any country. The teachers' motivation and learning environment due to academic development relatively need to be focused in the process of teaching and learning. Scorza [6] further stated that the classroom and the psychological state of the teachers has an input on students' chances to acquire knowledge. As stated by Otieno [7], availability of conducive teaching and learning environment on teachers' motivation promotes the effectiveness of schools and these are fundamental principles that will produce good academic achievement on the learners. Good management of both human and non-human resources promote effective performance among school employees [8]. That is if school teachers have been adequately taken care of with full support of the management, teachers in discharging their duties will engender success performance and job satisfaction. All educational establishments or organisations are occupied by both human and other non-human resources. When the appropriate quality and quantity of human resources have been harnessed together and properly motivated, they can manipulate other resources towards realizing stated goals [9]. Motivation has to do with the power and determination to carry out and achieve stated goals effectively. Therefore, motivation of teachers is very crucial as it directly influences students' academic performance positively [10]. Motivation as viewed by Scorza [6] is the process of impacting or enhancing an individual to pursue action that will determine the desired goals. Teachers' motivation therefore is a method of driving teachers in their profession as it involves their strategies, variables, methods, prospects and other approaches used by the management for the purpose of creating an enabling environment that is conducive for the actualization of the different needs of workers, so that they may become fulfilled, effective and dedicated in performing their tasks. Motivating teacher helps to enhance their effectiveness, efficiency, dedication and productivity in achieving certain tasks that would promote qualitative education and adequate instructional lesson delivery in the educational processes. It will also increase the performance level of educational goals and objectives [11]. Also, Sunday [8] see *motivation* as animated and insistent goal-directed behavior. According to Hanus *et al* [1], teacher motivation is a veritable tool that has a cardinal input on learners' performance. The level to which teachers are able to influence their learners is determined by how motivated they are [9]. High level of motivation may also advance teachers' efficacy and effectiveness that may bring about positive academic performance of students [10]. Low motivation may inform lack of interest, under-performance, transfer request to other schools and enhanced hostility to other school officials [12].

Effectiveness of teaching personnel as said by Triyanto [10] can be enhanced through various ways which include conducive school environment, prompt payment of salary and allowances, provision for teacher's educational development. The difference in individual's job performance as stated by Taiwo [13] has to do with motivational incentives which could be financial or non-financial. Both are however important factors in satisfying teachers' needs. Motivation is therefore an important issue in enhancing teachers' effectiveness as in schools, it increases the desire to work and participate in the pedagogical processes. The school is the bedrock of learning established for transmission of all aspects of learning, culturally and morally with the aim of achieving functional and effective education. It is therefore imperative that teachers should be stimulated through the various motivational incentives [12].

A number of studies have been done in the area of motivation for teachers and its benefits towards better performance for the students. For example, Ayuba [14] examined motivation and job satisfaction among private secondary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. Jikka [15] studied the influence of motivation on the teachers' job performance in Nigerian Secondary schools. Eyare [4] studied the influence of motivation on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Sub-county, Homa-bay County, Kenya. Garudzo-Kusereka [16] also studied influence of motivation on workers job performance in public institutions in Amagoro Sub-county, among others. Taiwo [13] conducted researcher on salary and condition of promotion as motivations for teacher's Job performance. The study concluded the more prompt payment of salary the higher would be job performance and the more favourable the condition of promotion the higher would workers or teachers performance in the school.

The purpose of this study was to examine motivation and teachers effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area.

Five research questions were asked based on the research problem ; (a) what is the level of teachers' motivation in public secondary school in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State?, (b) what is the level of teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State?, (c) what is the relationship between motivation and teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State?, (d) is there any difference in the teachers' motivation in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State based on gender?, and (e) is there any difference

in teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State based on gender?

Research hypotheses; (a) H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between motivation and teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State, (b) H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the teachers' motivation in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State based on gender, (c) H_{03} : There is no significant difference in teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State based on gender.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population comprised 150 randomly selected school principals and teachers from sampled schools across Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State. Random sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. The instrument that was used for collecting data for this study was adopted from Ayuba (2017) titled Motivation and Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire (MTEQ). The instrument was divided into three sections, namely: Section A, B and C. the statements were responded to with Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) response format. The responses were patterned after the 4 points- Likert rating scale. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by specialists in Educational Psychology and Evaluation and Measurement in the Department of Social Sciences Education, University of Ilorin. The test-re-test method with a time interval of two weeks was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. This instrument was adjudged suitable for the study with reliability coefficient of 0.69. The questionnaire were administered by the researcher and collected after they had been filled with the help of two research assistants. Data collected for the study were analysed using appropriate statistical analysis. Frequency counts and simple percentage, mean score and standard deviation were used to analysed the demographic section of the study while Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) and the t-test were employed to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results obtained from the statistical analysis of data are presented as follows:

Table 1 shows that out of the 150 teachers that involved in the study, 61 representing 40.7% of the respondents were male, while 89 representing 59.3% of the respondents were female. This shows that there were less male participants than their female counterparts.

Table 1. Distribution of the respondents by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	61	40.7
Female	89	59.3
Total	150	100

a. Answering of Research Questions

Five research questions were postulated, research question 1 and 2 were addressed using cumulative mean, while research questions 3 to 5 had corresponding hypotheses which were tested using PPMC and independent t-test.

Research Question 1: *What is the level of teachers' motivation in Ilorin West?*

In answering this research question, responses of the teachers to items on the teachers' motivational strategies questionnaire were collated. The output of the analysis reveals thus:

Research Question 2: *What is the level of teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West?*

In answering this research question, responses of the teachers to items on the teachers' effectiveness questionnaire were collated. The output of the analysis reveals thus:

Table 2 indicates that 150 respondents participated in this study. Responses to items that sought information on teachers' motivational strategies in Ilorin West Local Government area, Kwara State showed that majority of the teachers' motivational strategies is high because the benchmark weighted mean score stood at 40.0 and their weighted mean score is 42.26 which is above the benchmark weighted mean score.

Table 2: Cumulative mean level of teachers' motivational strategies in Ilorin West local government area, Kwara State

S/N	MOTIVATION	MEAN
1	Apart from my salary, the incentives I receive are enough to boost my morale on the job	2.53
2	Conducive working environment is essential for me to put in my best	2.39
3	It is important for school authorities to make adequate provision for my physiological and basic needs	2.77
4	Adequate in-service training enhances my dedication to work	2.82
5	Regular payment of my salary makes me to concentrate on my job	2.67
6	My school provides adequate security for me on the job and protects me against students' abuse or physical harm	2.3
7	Proper communication between the school management and member of staff improves my pace of work in the school	2.46
8	Discord and incessant quarrelling reduces my motivational level	2.49
9	Frequent rise in pay in my place of work usually gears me up	2.5
10	My institution recognizes workers' remarkable performance	2.15
11	In my school, each staff is important	2.52
12	Absence of cordial relationship between my superior and I makes work becomes tiring	3.03
13	Regular payment of staff salary contributes to peaceful atmosphere and harmonious relationship in my school	3.23
14	Lack of motivation by my management constitute to the fall in my morale	3.14
15	Team work is a stimulating factor for me in my school	3.34
16	Staff training and development contributes positively to my job performance	1.92
	Weighted Mean Score	42.26

Research Question 2: *What is the level of teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West?*

In order to answer this research question, responses of the teachers to items on the teachers' effectiveness questionnaire were collated. The output of the analysis reveals thus:

Table 3 indicates that 150 respondents participated in this study. Responses on items that sought information on teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local Government area showed that majority of the teachers' effectiveness was low because the benchmark weighted mean score stood at 50.0 and their weighted mean score is 45.05 which is below the benchmark weighted mean score.

Table 3. Cumulative mean level of teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local government area

S/N	STATEMENT	MEAN
1	I have full authority on the subject I am teaching	2.74
2	Besides my teaching subject, I have the ability to teach other needed subjects like current events , general knowledge etc.	2.42
3	I advise the students to solve their problems according to their needs	2.24
4	I give due opportunities to the students for proper motivation	2.76
5	I use more rewards and lesser punishment in the classroom for achievement of desired aims	2.46
6	A lengthy curriculum does not allow a teacher to use teaching aids or black board	2.54
7	I use civilized language with the students	2.51
8	I am well prepared when I come for teaching	2.19
9	I always appreciate student's opinions and demands	2.01
10	I admit my mistakes, pointed out by students willingly	1.9
11	I respect the head of institution as our senior most member	2.04
12	I listen patient, even the irrelevant question of the student and try to solve them	2.06
13	I co-operate willingly in the daily assignment of the school	2.23
14	A teacher cannot behave equally to all the students	1.89
15	I have enough self-confidence	1.95
16	I keep friendly and brotherly relationship with my teacher colleagues	2.28
17	I have respectfully with all guardians without discriminating case, social status and economic status etc	2.27
18	One cannot be always punctual	2.04
19	It is very cumbersome to check all homework notebooks regularly	2.09
20	I co-operate with the guardian to solve the problem of student for their proper development according to the right opportunity	2.43
	Weighted Mean Score	45.05

b. Hypotheses testing

Three research hypotheses were formulated for this study, hypothesis one was tested using the PPMC, while research hypotheses two and three were tested using the independent t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

H_{01} : *There is no significant relationship between motivation and teachers effectiveness in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State.*

In testing this research hypothesis, respondents' responses to motivation and teachers' effectiveness questionnaires were collated. The data collated from the study were analysed as revealed in Table 4.

Table 4. PPMC Analysis of the relationship between motivation and teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West local government area, Kwara State

Variables	No	Mean	Std	df	Cal.r	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Motivation	150	39.67	12.29				
Effectiveness	150	51.38	18.58				
				148	0.12	0.15	Not Rejected

$P < 0.05$

As indicated on Table 4, the calculated r-value was 0.12 while its calculated significance value is 0.15 at alpha level of 0.05. On this basis, the null hypothesis one was therefore retained. Therefore, it means that there was no significant relationship between motivation and teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West. The reason was that the calculated significance value (0.15) was greater than 0.05 alpha level ($0.15 > 0.05$).

H_{02} : *There is no significant difference between teachers' motivation in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State based on gender.*

In testing this research hypothesis, respondents' responses to motivation and teachers' effectiveness questionnaires were collated. The data collected from the study was analysed as presented in Table 5.

Table 5. T-test of differences between male and female teachers' motivation in Ilorin West local government area, Kwara State based on gender

Variables	No	Mean	Std	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Male	61	41.82	12.59				
Female	89	38.19	11.92				
				148	1.79	0.08	Not Rejected

$P < 0.05$

Table 5 revealed that the calculated t-value was 1.79 while its calculated significance value is 0.08 at alpha level of 0.05. on this basis, the null hypothesis two was therefore retained. This indicates that there was no significant difference in the teachers' motivation in Ilorin West Local Government based on gender. The reason was that the calculated significance value (0.08) was greater than 0.05 alpha level.

H_{02} : *There is no significant difference in teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government area of Kwara State based on gender*

In order to test this research hypothesis, respondents' responses to teachers' effectiveness section of the questionnaires were collated and analysed. The data collected from the study were analysed as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. T-test of differences in male and female teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local government area, Kwara State based on gender

Variables	No	Mean	Std	df	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Male	61	41.82	12.59				
Female	89	51.85	18.71				
				148	0.38	0.71	Not Rejected

$P < 0.05$

b. Discussion

The study investigated influence of motivation on teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local Government area, Kwara State. The first finding showed that the teachers' level of motivation in Ilorin West Local Government Area was slightly above average. This finding is in line with that [17, 18] who reported that teachers' motivation in public secondary schools was average. This means that, when motivation is average and above, it allows teachers to put in more effort in discharging their task. However, the results of these findings negate that of Weiss et al and Reeve et al [19, 20] who reported that the level of motivation of teachers in many schools across Nigeria were poor.

Another finding showed that the level of teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West was low. This outcome is not tandem with that of Cheney [21] who affirmed that there was average teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools. The difference in the findings could be as a result of differences in the locale. The result of the study also in consonant with the study of Omag [22] which revealed that motivation was crucial in enhancing teachers' commitment to job performance amongst public secondary school teachers in Rachuonyo South Sub-county.

The third finding showed that there was no significant relationship between motivation and teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West. This finding differs from the finding of Ibechukwu [23] who found out that, there was significant relationship between teachers' effectiveness and motivation in public and private secondary schools. The outcome of the study is also contrary to the finding of Ogundele [24] which revealed that there is a positive association (0.444) amid working condition and performance of agricultural science teachers.

Another finding shows that, there was no significant difference in the teachers' motivation in Ilorin West Local Government based on gender. This finding is not in agreement with the finding of Martin [25] who conducted a study on teacher motivation based on their tenure, gender and level of education and found out that female teachers' motivation is higher than the male teachers. The difference in the two findings may be as a result of sentiments female teachers attached teaching profession as the only perceived profession that allows the females to have time to cater for their home.

4. CONCLUSION

The research investigated the influence of motivation on teachers' effectiveness in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara, Nigeria. The result revealed that teachers' motivation level was slightly above average level. It was also revealed that teachers' effectiveness in their instructional strategies was low. The study found out that there was no significant relationship between motivation and teachers' effectiveness. In conclusion, teachers motivation and their effectiveness are not directly correlated and high level of motivation may not determine high level of effectiveness on the job.

Based on the outcome of this study therefore, it was recommended that; regular supervision and assessment of teachers is needed so as to put them up and doing and this may in turn increase effectiveness in the teaching profession. Regular increase in teachers' salary should be provided so as to cater for high standard of living and hyper inflation. There is the need to adequately review the general wellbeing of the teachers based on their condition of service prepare by the Ministries of Education and other government agencies in the education sector.

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